

Regenerative Sanitation: A Conceptual Framework towards Transforming Sanitation Service Improvement and Access Expansion

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Abstract: This paper presents the Regenerative Sanitation concept and framework, a comprehensive, holistic, integrated and systemic outlook for sanitation management that embraces the dynamic complexities and contextual peculiarities of 'place and scale' in delivering sanitation solutions. The framework was developed using mixed methods content analysis, experiential knowledge, and review of applicable cases. The framework serves to provide better understanding of the knowledge interconnections among the sanitation sub-systems, dimensions and components; provides comprehensive, explorative, experimental and descriptive assessments using qualitative and quantitative datasets as well as integrate science-policy-technology-practice research into the sanitation space. It proposes perspectives from three angles (socio-ecological, resource recovery and technology) with dimensions of psycho-socio-ecophilia, governance, resource recovery/reuse, existing-improved, restorative and new design and technology in order to address sanitation in a systemic and practical approach. The regenerative sanitation advocates for technology solutions that include user interface, storage and treatment processes and resource recovery/utilization as a subsystem. In addition, it proposes the concept of sani-sheds designed to enhance significant cost-saving and benefit-sharing as well as the principle of no-transfer-of-burden whereby final waste transportation from location of generation is minimally reduced. The framework is broad enough to accommodate other pre-existing frameworks and perspectives as it provides functional and progressive approaches towards improving and expanding access to sanitation services at a 'scale'. It could really provide the much-needed improvement and mind-change in sanitation system-thinking, management, planning and technology innovations without compromising ecosystem sustainability. Ultimately, the regenerative sanitation will lead to research that provides more practical solutions for effective sanitation management and service delivery as well as guide policy transformation and effective funding/intervention programs. Some areas for future research were suggested.

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1. Introduction

Fifteen years of the MDGs still left an estimated 2.3 billion people with unimproved sanitation facilities (lacking basic services) and about 892 million practicing open defecation (Joint Monitoring Programme 2015, Gine-Garriga et al. 2017, O'Reilly et al. 2017). This burden is carried forward in the SDG, which has tightened the expectations beyond 'halving' to universal access (WHO/UNICEF 2017). This has created a global urgency for improving service and expanding access to sanitation. This global challenge is made evident as most adjudged 'improved' sewer systems have questionable treatment efficiencies and efficacies with no standard solutions for retrofitting (Goodland et al. 2001, Schertenleib 2005, Stenström et al. 2011, Maurer et al. 2012, Starkl et al. 2013, Ekane et al. 2014, WWAP 2017, Brepols et al. 2008, Bozkurt et al. 2015), while 'improved' onsite technologies still pose a burden of ineffective faecal sludge management (Kalbermatten et al. 1980, Kalbermatten et al. 1982, Franceys et al. 1992, UNESCO/IHP and GTZ 2006, Barrenberg and Stenström 2010, Thye et al. 2011, [EcoSan Club](#) 2011, Banerjee and Morella 2011, Berger 2011, Chowdhry and Kone 2012, WHO/UNICEF 2013, AIT 2013/2015, Hawkins and Muximpua 2015, Jenkins et al. 2014, Chunga 2016, Bongartz et al. 2016) for the 2.7 billion people globally served by these systems (Kone 2010, Koné et al. 2010, Kvarnström et al. 2012, Niwagaba et al. 2014, Blackett et al. 2014), particularly in developing countries. In addition, lack of treatment services often result in unsafe disposal (Eawag/Sandec 2006, UNICEF/WHO 2012, Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation 2012, Nikiema et al. 2014, AIT 2013/2015, Taweesan et al. 2015a/b, Rao et al. 2016), which implies increased exposure to disease-causing pathogens from human excreta with well-established associated health risks (Cairncross and Feachem 1993, Boschi-Pinto et al. 2006, Ekane et al. 2014). Developed countries also face twin challenges of retrofitting and upgrading aging and decaying infrastructure as well as transiting from rigid knocked-in conventional centralized sanitation technologies towards flexible and 'regenerative' forms of sanitation (Brands 2014, Butler and Parkinson 1997, Drangert 1998, Delleur 2003, Wilsenach et al. 2003, Bracken et al. 2006, Ashley et al. 2011, WWAP 2017). Invariably, both worlds will need to move beyond traditional dichotomies of small and large/appropriate, modern conventional, sewer and non-sewer, centralized or decentralized technologies (van Vliet et al. 2011, Brands 2014, Raymond et al. 2016).

Sanitation needs to be addressed with the same level of importance accorded water supply to ensure a balanced progress (World Water Council 2012) and this requires a focused-adaptable perspective. Meeting MDG targets for water could be trailed through paradigm shifts of past decades from mechanistic-technocratic command and control, which neglect complexities and the human dimension, to more adaptive and integrated approaches (Holling and Meffe 1996, GWP-TAC 2000, Braga 2001, GWP 2004, Medema et al. 2008, Pahl-Wostl et al. 2010/2011, Engle et al. 2011, Hailbe et al. 2013). In the same trend, critical voices have called for paradigm shifts ranging from current techno-centric approaches of sanitation to more holistic, integrated and transdisciplinary perspectives (Mara and Alabaster 2008, van Vliet and Spaargaren 2010, van Vliet et al. 2011, Maurer et al. 2012, Marshall and Farahbakhsh 2013, Starkl et al. 2013, Tilley et al. 2014a, Wielemaker et al. 2016, Fan et al. 2017) where all the sub-systems, dimensions and components of sanitation are inter-synergistically linked together to improve service delivery and expand access. The shifts could be viewed from an ecological worldview that aligns human development efforts with nature's potential to repair damages done to the biosphere and strategies that provide innovative solutions based on regenerative design principles (Lyle 1994, Thayer 1994, Mang and Reed 2012a, Cole 2012). The aim would be to restore and retrofit previously unimproved or damaged sanitation facilities, ensure continuous intensified operations and maintenance to improve performance, as well as incorporating resource recovery and reuse into the existing improved and new sanitation systems. This paper introduces the regenerative sanitation (ReGenSan) for service improvement, access expansion and sustainability. The regenerative concept has been extensively used in the fields of biological and medical sciences, urban development, architectural design and the built environment, but not to sanitation management yet.

Sanitation systems, much like water systems, are complex dynamic processes with influence-interactions between the physical, social, economic and ecological components (Seadon 2006/2010, Mele et al. 2010, Tilley et al. 2014a) that lean towards an ecological worldview (Hes and du Plessis 2014, du Plessis and Braandon 2015). Ecological worldview, unlike the mechanistic worldview, requires that we 'listen and learn' from nature's ways of resource recycling since in nature nothing is considered waste (McHarg 1969, Guterstam and Todd 1990, Mitsch 1993, Mitsch and Jorgensen 1989, Kibert et al. 2002, Graham 2003, Van der Ryn and Cowan 2007, Mitsch and Jorgensen 2003). However, past paradigms and foundations of sanitation management have been based on the mechanistic-worldview, which focuses primarily on techno-solutions. Providing improved services and expanding access to sanitation goes beyond techno-solutions and innovative management by including increased participation and combination of other psychological, social and ecological factors (Reymond et al. 2016, Rosenqvist et al. 2016). For instance, social failure of sanitation systems can be manifested by non-use or misuse of the technology caused by socio-cultural or socio-economic deficiencies such as lack of demand, acceptance or knowledge of use, unwillingness or inability to pay for services. Social deficiencies may also lead to environmental and hygiene risks (Starkl et al. 2013). Resource recovery from sanitation systems could also be affected by differences in social groups' values and attitudes. Therefore, the fundamental and persistent challenges in the sanitation sector as well as in literature should be to identify ways that existing proven approaches such as management and governance, technologies, social marketing and mobilization, financial mechanisms among others can be used holistically and this could effectively help guide the thinking of practitioners, policy makers and academia (World Water Council 2012). Therefore, a holistic and integrated framework that captures the essence of sanitation as solutions rather than as 'arbiter of evil' to be eradicated from other areas (water, health, hygiene, environment) will put the journey towards SDG 6 on alert speed, which is the intent of this paper.

1.1 Sanitation paradigms

Paradigm set operational and intellectual boundaries and guidelines for investigation and interpreting scientific solutions as well as technological phenomena (Kuhn 1962, Leclerc 2005, Pahl-Wostl 2011, Halbe et al. 2013). Over time progressive and changing trends and conditions constrain existing paradigms' efficacy and make them inadequate and/or redundant (Mara and Alabaster 2008, Rosenqvist et al. 2016). Thus, a paradigm shift becomes necessary to capture current and prevailing conditions and thoughts for sound logical reasoning and effective interpretation/implementation. Sanitation paradigms (SaPs) are the different accepted forms and approaches of conceptualizing and handling sanitation management and technology over the years. A SaP trails processes and systems development for research, technology and management design and implementation of sanitation solutions and services. Most SaPs are techno-centric, resource-oriented, service-oriented, water-use-focused, participatory-focused and behavioral-change focused. There have, however, been calls for a paradigm shift, especially with the dismal results of the sanitation targets in the MDGs and the tightened expectations in the SDG.

The rationale for this call for a paradigm shift include:

- I. Sanitation systems are increasingly recognized as complex and integrated processes between physical, social, economic, ecological and technological aspects (Schubber 1996, Seadon 2006, Spaaragaren et al. 2007, van Vliet et al. 2011, Marshall and Farahbakhsh 2013, IWA 24:2016);
- II. Contextual factors such as culture, economy, institutional control, and climate are considered as critical elements that can affect public acceptance of technical and infrastructural feasibility for innovation (Whittington et al. 1993, Larsen et al. 2010, Domènech and Saurí 2010, McConville et al. 2014);

- III. Technological development processes and approaches are now highly contextual and dependent on a number of socio-cultural-economic and ecological factors (Raven 2007, Hegger et al. 2007, McConville et al. 2014, Balkema et al. 2002);
- IV. Nature-based solutions such as ecological engineering and eco-technologies are now known to represent plausible sustainable approaches for solving the global sanitation problems, especially the use of constructed wetlands and other ecosystem solutions (Guterstam and Todd 1990, Mahmood et al. 2013, European Commission 2015, Nesshover et al. 2017, Polprasert and Koottatep 2017, Lens et al. 2001, Vymazal 2005, Barros et al. 2008, Mahmood et al. 2013, Elzein et al 2016, Wu et al. 2016);
- V. Governance is considered a critical success and supporting mechanism that provides the enabling environment for effective and efficient service delivery, and financing sustainability (Schertenleib 2005, Maurer et al. 2012, Speer et al. 2012, Hallerod et al. 2013, Rodic 2015, Joshi et al. 2015);
- VI. Resource recovery and reuse are acknowledged as key components of comprehensive integrated sanitation solutions with the potential for natural resource conservation and has the capacity to leverage the long-term efficacy of treatment schemes and livelihood support (Benetto et al. 2009, Werner et al. 2009, Murray and Buckley 2009, USEPA 2012, Nikiema et al. 2014, Keraita et al. 2014, Hu et al 2016, Otoo et al. 2016, Rao et al. 2016, Cofie et al. 2016, WWAP 2017);
- VII. Technology-based indicators for determining 'improved' and 'unimproved' sanitation instead of functional-service based indicators constrain innovation (Kuznyestsov 2007, Sutton 2008, Kvarnstrom 2011, Werner and Fischer 2007, WSP 2008, Larsen et al. 2010, Domènech and Saurí 2010, Potter et al. 2011, van Vliet et al 2011, Banerjee and Morella 2011, McConville et al. 2014); and
- VIII. Inadequate and dysfunctional sanitation infrastructures are due to structural inadequacies, material degradation, poor construction and workmanship as well as aging facilities and lack of appropriate operations and maintenance (Brikke 2000, Brepolsa et al. 2008, Cooney et al. 2016a). These dysfunctions and inadequacies are costly for society and its economic impacts are estimated to cost 18 African countries a colossal sum of USD 5.5 billion per year (Pruss et al. 2002, UNDP 2006, Prüss-Üstün et al. 2008, Fewtrell et al. 2005, Yardley 2010, Cheng et al. 2012, Bartram and Cairncross 2010, Bos and Gijzen 2005, WSP 2012, Ekane et al. 2014). Strategic and innovative plans and programmes to retrofit these systems could accelerate the targets of SDG 6 on sanitation.

The major paradigms that have influenced sanitation research, science, technology, management policy and practice can be categorised into a historical timeline. Sanitation solutions have travelled through history starting from the time of open defecation to the need for privacy as well as keeping faecal matter out of sight (accumulated in pits, dumping into rivers or shovelling into fields) (Cooper 2001, Persson 2017, Zeldovich 2017, O'Reilly et al. 2017). Overtime, the trends have graduated from one level to another and produced several kinds of technological solutions: conventional sanitation (sanitation 1.0); ecological sanitation (sanitation 2.0); sustainable sanitation (sanitation 3.0); and ReGenSan (sanitation 4.0). These solutions can be themed according to the era of their introduction (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Sanitation paradigms, frameworks, technologies and international milestones

(I) *Conventional sanitation (sanitation 1.0)* - is the 'flush and discharge' or 'drop and store' technology based on the premise that excreta is waste suitable only for disposal. This concept is based on the assumption of linear flow of resources that is ultimately wasted and disposed of, making recycling impossible (Esrey 2001, Andersson et al. 2016). Although, there are innovative approaches of this system incorporating resource recovery and reuse as incremental improvement strategies, paradigm shifts are being advocated for overcoming these challenges, especially through the adoption of integrated sanitation solutions that go above and beyond the focus of technology (Larsen 2011, Otterpohl 2002, Geels 2006, Zeeman et al. 2008, Marshall and Farahbakhsh 2013, Tilley et al. 2014, Thibodeau et al. 2014) (Figure 2).

Figure 2 Sanitation 1.0 – linear flow system of the conventional sanitation concept for sewer and non-sewer systems

(i) *Ecological sanitation (sanitation 2.0)* - is resource-oriented, ecological and source separation based on closure of material flow cycle and sewage disposal to resources reclamation. It is a re-conceptualization of conventional sanitation from 'flush and discharge' to 'drop and reuse' models (Haq and Cambridge, 2012; Langergraber and Muellegger, 2005, Hu et al. 2016) and is designed to close the nutrient loop between sanitation and agriculture even though the technologies are not ecological per se (Werner et al. 2009, Langergraber and Muellegger 2005, Esrey 2001, Werner et al. 2004). The major draw-back is basically the cost and cultural constraints on the usage of treated excreta and sewage (Hu et al. 2016) (Figure 3).

Figure 3 Sanitation 2.0 – circular flow system of resource oriented/ecological sanitation

(I) *Sustainable sanitation (sanitation 3.0)* – is a holistic approach to sanitation that recognizes not only technology, but also social, environmental and economic aspects with the same goal as ecological sanitation (SUSANA 2008). The core principles include: human health protection, affordability, environmental sustainability and institutional appropriateness (Mara et al. 2007, Chinyama et al. 2012). It was designed to address the challenges of conventional sanitation by adopting the generic principles of sustainable development (SD), but is limited in that sanitation management should not be over-simplified (Marshall and Farahbakhsh 2013) (Figure 4).

Figure 4 Sanitation 3.0 – Principles of sustainable sanitation

Much progress could not be achieved with the last two paradigms because of the technological lock-in-situation created by the conventional approaches (Biswas 2004, Pahl-Wostl 2007, Pahl-Wostl et al. 2011), which has been described as the dictatorial tendencies of conventional sanitation that impedes the needed paradigm shift (Fan et al. 2017). However, effecting a paradigm shift will require conceptualizing an integrative, holistic and comprehensive framework that logically assigns inter-synergistic connections and interactions through well-articulated core principles.

1.2 Sanitation frameworks

A framework is a domain-specific language tailored to specific knowledge area or discipline of study (Bently 1986, Abelson and Sussman 1987, Hudak 1998, Hinkel et al. 2014). The elements of a framework are concepts which are terms associated with a meaning and the conceptual relationship between them (Hinkel et al. 2014). Therefore, a conceptual framework facilitates the exchange of arguments about a knowledge domain through having clear and unambiguous accounts of the concepts at stake and their relationships (Hinkel 2008, Ionescu et al. 2009, Wolf et al. 2013). Sanitation conceptual frameworks (SCF) will provide the premises and the parameters for research, investigations, interpretation, development of programmes and implementation of action plans for improving service and expanding access to meet the SDG 6 by 2030.

A SCF will lay out key factors, constructs or variables, and presume the relationships among them (Miles and Huberman 1994, Campbell et al. 2015) as well as provide a template used for acknowledging and organizing the elements of related systems of interest to support further investigations. They will also illustrate the connected parts and potential interdependencies between broad system variables (Binder et al. 2013, Repella 2014) and support the formulations and comparisons of hypothesis, models, and theories as well as provide general sets of concepts assumed to be applicable to the whole (Ostrom 2005). The goal of such framework development is to stay as neutral as possible to allow the representation of different theories within the framework (Hinkel et al. 2014). Existing conceptual frameworks in the field of sanitation can be grouped into eight major categories:

- I. *Sanitation ladder* - the most popular and one of the oldest, which has been used in so many forms and cases ranging from toilets/latrines provision, full service chain delivery, hygiene behavior, human right issues, financing sanitation, latrine ownership and MDG/SDG Joint Monitoring Programmes as well as in the community-led total sanitation for the eradication of open defecation (Kar and Chambers 2008, Joint Monitoring Programme 2010, Potter et al. 2011, Kvarnström et al. 2011, Gine et al. 2011, Verhagen and Carrasco 2013, Exley et al. 2014, Obeng et al. 2015, WHO/UNICEF 2017, O'Reilly et al. 2017);

- ii. *Sanitation service chain* - used in the analysis of physical flow of faecal waste through sewer and non-sewer systems, development of faecal waste flow matrix and diagrams to summarize city or community level outcomes and highlight bottleneck in faecal waste management. It is also used for business analysis of faecal sludge management and in the development of the global sanitation service technology filter tool (Trémolet and Rama 2012, Chowdhry and Kone 2012, Strande et al. 2014, Blackett et al. 2014, WSP 2014, Rao et al. 2016, USAID 2016).
- iii. *Decision support* - used in designs, testing, selections, sustainability and performance modelling of technologies from centralized to decentralized sanitation systems (Kalbermatten et al. 1980/1982, Loetscher and Keller 2002, Zurbrugg and Tilley 2007, Magid et al. 2006, Zurbrugg and Tilley 2009, Massoud et al. 2009, Katukiza, et al. 2010/2012, Stenström et al. 2011, Maurer et al. 2012, Libralato et al. 2012, McConville et al. 2014, Tilley et al. 2014b, Ramoa et al. 2015, Roefs et al. 2017, Simha et al. 2017, Tobias et al. 2017);
- iv. *Designing for service* - focused on resource utilization options of sanitation systems. These include concepts that deal with resource-oriented sanitation, recovery and reuse, integrated resource management, cradle-to-cradle, ecological sanitation, circular flow as well as recirculation of nutrients and organic matter (McDonough and Braungart 2001a/b, Wilsenach et al. 2003, Hodges 2006, Wang et al. 2006, Langergraber and Muellegger 2005, Larsen et al. 2009, Murray, and Buckley 2009, Werner et al. 2009, Brands 2014, Wielemaker et al. 2016);
- v. *Spatial planning diagnostics* - provides approaches and methodologies for detailed assessment of sanitation situations of regions, cities, urban, formal, and informal settlement as well as rural areas to determine appropriate levels of intervention activities for program implementation (GHK Research and Training 2000, ASHWAS 2011, Lüthi et al. 2011 a/b, Parkinson et al. 2014, IWA 2014, ISF-UTS and SNV 2016, Bright-Davies et al. 2016, Kerstens et al. 2016, Schmitt et al. 2017);
- vi. *Equity and inclusion* - designed to improve access to sanitation services by the vulnerable groups and people with disabilities in the society (Gosling 2010, Patkar and Gosling 2011, Desai et al. 2016);
- vii. *Behavioural change* – this software tool is used in various sanitation, hygiene and handwashing programmes as well as sanitation solutions adoption and uptake (Whittington et al. 1993, Peal et al. 2010, Dreibelbis et al. 2013, O'Reilly and Louis 2014, Dwipayanti et al. 2017); and
- viii. *Capacity development assessment* – designed to assess effectiveness and efficiency of sanitation capacity development programs (Mvulirwenande et al. 2013, Gunawardana et al. 2013, Pascual Sanz et al. 2013, Barat et al. 2014, Ngai et al. 2014, Crocker et al. 2016)

These conceptual frameworks, however, are primarily techno-focused and basically designed for implementation of conventional sanitation. An integrated sanitation conceptual framework that embraces the complexities inherent in providing sanitation solutions rather than simplistic recipes would enhance service delivery (Meinzen-Dick 2007, Pahl-Wostl 2007, Pahl-Wostl et al. 2010). Hence, the main contribution of this paper is to provide a holistic integrated sanitation conceptual framework (or model) that is not techno-centric and toilet-latrine-focused; but where all key critical aspects of sanitation sub-systems and dimensions are inter-linked for the development and implementations of innovative solutions.

Providing comprehensive sanitation solutions for the current global challenges depend not only on availability of technology, but also on many other factors like management of sanitation delivery, quality of institutions that manage them, prevailing psycho-socio-cultural, economic and ecological conditions that influence sanitation planning, technology design and development, management processes and practice, financial and governance mechanism (Zurbrugg and Tilley 2009, Tilley et al. 2014a, Starkl et al. 2015). In this paper, sanitation systems (sanisystem) are referred to as systemic integration of measures towards managing human waste in a safe and resourceful pattern adapted to fit specific and peculiar contexts. It is a systemic integration in that it flows from the 'place' of human interactions (psycho-socio-cultural-economic) with the ecosystem (ecological, bio-geo-physical) to interconnect with the governance subsystem (regulatory mechanisms-standards), resource recovery appraisal subsystem (recovery/reuse of excreta-urine-flush water-black/grey water) and technology subsystem

(infrastructure-utilities) with the singular aim of improving service and expanding access to proper sanitation. The issue at the moment is not whether such an approach is desirable, but rather how can this be achieved in the real world? The central idea is the need for broader integration with all the system components of sanitation, minimized transport, local-orientation and decentralization, source separation and resource recovery, management and governance (Lens et al. 2001, Kujawa-Roeveld and Zeeman 2006, Larsen et al. 2009, Maurer et al. 2012, Zeeman 2012, Agudelo-Vera et al. 2012, van Vliet et al 2010/2011, Nansubuga et al. 2016).

Several scholars and practitioners have suggested that the proposed paradigm shift should be holistic, integrated, multidimensional and transdisciplinary (Zeeman 2009, Seadon 2010, van Vliet et al. 2011, Marshall and Farahbakhsh 2013, Galli et al. 2014). They also propose some nomenclatures for this new paradigm, but did not really come out with a clear framework to guide this transition. For instance, Wielemaker et al. (2016) and Agudelo-Vera et al. (2012) called it 'new sanitation'; Fan et al. (2017) proposed 'sanitation 2.0'; Heggart (2007) and van Vliet et al. (2010/2011) named it 'hybrid or modernized mixture'; Verstraete et al. (2009) and Nansubuga et al. (2016) suggested 'cluster decentralized systems', and Marshall and Farahbakhsh (2013), Tilley et al. (2014) proposed 'integrated approach'; while Galli et al. (2014) suggested 'whole system approach'. However, the focus is still on technology and 'frameworks' are known to behave and influence according to how they are named. In addition, without clear directives on operational guidance, these well-intentioned proposals get lost within old systems and paradigms.

Therefore, a paradigm shift in sanitation service delivery and management called ReGenSan is proposed to capture the essence of the change we advocate beyond technology systems. This paper presents the ReGenSan conceptual framework that is Sanitation 4.0. (Figure 8). ReGenSan is a transition from the old way to a new way that incorporates aspects of the old with the new in a transdisciplinary approach. Regenerative is a phrase used here to mean complete revitalization and rejuvenation of the entire sanitation system to improve service and expand access as well as the deliberate partnership with nature. This ReGenSan is conceptualized based on the principles of systemic internal processes for restoration and sustainability and addresses sanitation as a comprehensive and holistic integrated system incorporating all the unique characteristics of sani-management from the starting point of a specific and peculiar 'place' (location). It sees sanitation as resource/service management rather than problem management. At its core is a process trail that works from within the system and the peculiarities of the 'place' to ensure resilience and adaptability. ReGenSan is at the same time a paradigm framework and perspective for sanitation solutions.

The overall aim of ReGenSan is to refocus the perspectives of researchers, professionals, practitioners, advocacy-agents, policy makers and solution-providers from attacking a problem to providing a service and solutions; and ultimately, expand access as well as improve service towards achieving the SDG 6 by 2030. The corresponding conceptual framework presented in this paper is designed to reflect the process for the kind of sanitation practice that would fulfill this ambitious goal. This paper has been divided into four parts with the first part devoted to the introduction. The second part provides details of the study's methodology while the third part is devoted to the presentation of the conceptual framework, its implementation process followed by applicable cases and then discussion and conclusion.

2.0 METHODOLOGY

An iterative mixed methods approach was adopted in developing this framework by combining experiential knowledge (including technical knowledge and research background) and literature review that included previous related theories, researches and concepts that have been used to represent similar problems (Novak and Canas 2008, Campbell et al. 2015). The aim was to develop a holistic and integrative sanitation system framework to guide pursuit of the SDG 6 by 2030. This section discusses how the regenerative sanitation (ReGenSan) conceptual framework was developed. The ReGenSan paradigm proposes that research and design for sanitation should start from the 'place', reduce transfer of burden, be resource-oriented, conserve (produce) energy, incorporate restorative and continuous improvement principles.

The framing of the ReGenSan concept resulted from two research activities: (i) critical literature review using mixed content analysis approach (Brewerton and Millward 2001, Seuring and Muller 2008, Martinez-Jurado and Moyano-Fuentes 2014, Bocken et al. 2016) and (ii) cases and lessons learnt from the Bill & Melinda Gates

Foundation 'reinventing the toilet' research project on Sustainable Decentralized Wastewater Management (DEWAT) in Developing Countries implemented in Thailand, Vietnam, and Cambodia by the Asian Institute of Technology (AIT) (Koottatep et al. 2014, AIT 2013/2015, Pussayanavin et al. 2015, Koottatep et al. 2015, Fakkaew et al. 2015a/b, Koottatep et al. 2016) and other relevant cases around the world.

A four step methodological approach 'input-processing-output-outcome' detailed approach with rigorous sequential steps of activities (Sethi and King 1998, Levy and Ellis 2006) was followed. They include collation of relevant scientific and technical literature based on the objectives of the study; 'input' through using data techniques to select, know, comprehend, apply, analyze, synthesize and evaluate the information in order to provide a firm foundation to produce the desirable 'output' for the study (which is to frame the concept of regenerative sanitation as well as propose new area of research) and practical 'outcome' to improve and expand access to sanitation services towards achieving SDG 6 (Mayring 2003, Levy and Ellis 2006). The framework was iteratively reviewed by series of feedbacks and brainstorming sessions as well as trainings and workshop sessions within and outside AIT. Figure 5 provides a detailed schematic description of the process. Clear boundaries were set to ensure that the research approach of the study was lucid, transparent and synchronized with the purpose of the paper.

Figure 5 Methodology to develop Regenerative Sanitation conceptual framework

The revised bibliography includes peer reviewed journal articles, technical reports and textbooks in English language. The search for related publications was mainly conducted as keywords and terms used frequently in literature to describe and define the area of study of regenerative and sustainability sciences, sanitation, hygiene, handwashing, water and wastewater treatment, ecological engineering, governance, management and public health. Brainstorming by snow-balling were used to derive keywords and concepts. The major search databases were: Elsevier (www.sciencedirect.com), google scholar (<http://scholar.google.com>), Emerald (www.emeraldinsight.com), Springer (www.springerlink.com), Wiley (www.wiley.com), Taylor and Francis (www.taylorandfrancis.com), Scopus (www.scopus.com), Web of Science (www.webofknowledge.com), MDPI, (www.mdpi.com), PubMed (www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov), JSTORE (www.jstor.org), ACS publications (www.pubs.acs.org), ResearchGate (www.researchgate.net), International Water Association (www.iwapublishing.com/journals), IRC International Water and Sanitation Centre (www.ircwash.org) and Sustainable Sanitation Alliance (www.susana.org).

2.1 Content analysis

Content analysis was used to survey articles comprehensively. The first step was exploratory bibliometric analysis of publications using SCOPUS database, which indicated the number of papers that match each search term in each year (Pahl-Wostl et al. 2010). This was followed by evaluative and descriptive approaches used to classify papers, reports, and books. The contents of these publications were further assessed by means of descriptive analysis: distribution of the publication over timeframe, the journals or publishers of the publications and thematic focus and geographical spread (Brewerton and Millward 2001, Mayring 2003, Levy and Ellis 2006, Duriau et al. 2007, Seuring and Muller 2008, Martinez-Jurado and Moyano-Fuentes 2014, Bocken et al. 2016). Each article was examined to ensure that its contents were relevant from the perspective of the aims of our research. Cited references from the articles reviewed were used as secondary source, which did not yield much additional papers and could be an indicator of the validity of the research. To increase research reliability, databases and journals as well as individual papers were checked by two additional researchers (Seuring and Muller 2008, Martinez-Jurado and Moyano-Fuentes 2014).

3.0 DESCRIPTIVE ANALYSIS

3.1 Development of holistic integrated sanitation system (ReGenSan) research

The approach for the development of holistic integrated sanitation system research was adopted from Pahl-Wostl et al. (2011). Evidences from scientific literature have been provided in ongoing discourse for integrated sanitation system paradigm shift. To assess the current state of development in this direction, a bibliometric analysis of publications was conducted using SCOPUS database, applying different combination of keywords to define search terms. The resulting dataset records the number of publications in peer-reviewed journals in the search space (Pahl-Wostl et al. 2010).

Researches on sanitation primarily focus on technology and the impact of sanitation on health, hygiene and water. Publications on sanitation-related science show serious emphasis on technology over integrated systems and governance, including the increase in publications with integrated systems and governance in recent years. In the case of integrated sanitation systems, the publications grew from 14 in 2002 to over 44 in 2015; while sanitation management and governance grew from 2 publications in 2002 to 15 in 2016. There was also an increase in researches that focused on resource recovery and reuse. The data showed that not much researches with focus on retrofitting, rehabilitation and repairs of sanitation infrastructures were undertaken.

3.2 Distribution across the time and main journals

The database searches yielded 348 articles and other publications for the period analyzed (1974 - May 2017). The first publication with focus on living system thinking and the need to embrace the holistic and ecological worldview (Von Bertalanffy 1956) in designing human ecosystems (Lyle 1984) appeared in 1956. This was closely followed by regenerative design for sustainable development (Lyle 1994). Also, the first work in this study related to the theme of sanitation was published by Bahri (1999) with focus on reuse of wastewater. High number of publications were found within the period of 2001 to 2016 and were mainly sanitation-focused and probably influenced by the MDG 7 era (Figure 6).

The articles were differentiated into six categories in relation to sanitation publication. It should be mentioned that papers that cover more than one theme were ticked in their respective columns accordingly and in cases where all themes were covered, they were categorized as hybrid. The rationale for theme categorization was to determine the predominant sanitation research focus as an independent discipline when not attached to water, health, and engineering, but with the understanding that it is an interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary field of study. Conscious efforts were made not to include articles that had no particular sanitation focus. The theories and concepts that influenced the research and development of sanitation were investigated because science and technology progress faster when researches operate within explicit concepts and theories (Suppe 1977, Scheiner 2010). The number of publications that were technology-focused was assessed because several authors have expressed the fact that sanitation has been technology-dominant and for any meaningful improvement and expansion of services to occur, there will be a need to go beyond technology (Zeeman 2009, van Vliet et al. 2011, Tilley et al. 2014a). Hence, six thematic aspects were differentiated: (i) theories/concepts, (ii) technology, (iii) service delivery, (iv) social

perspectives, (v) governance and management, and (vi) hybrid (Figure 7). Among the 36 papers that dealt with theoretical and conceptual issues, sanitation as an independent discipline (not attached to health, water, hygiene and

engineering) came up as an emerging field of research. There were 125 papers focusing on technology, 23 on service delivery, 32 on social sciences and 40 on governance and management.

Figure 6 Distribution of publication per year across the period studied

Figure 7 Thematic content analysis of publications

4.0 THE REGENSAN FRAMEWORK

4.1 Conceptual basis for ReGenSan framework

There is need for an integrated systemic sanitation conceptual framework that is not techno-centric, but embraces dynamic complexities and contextual issues while delivering context-dependence integrated solutions. The increasing interest in psychosocio-cultural-economic-ecological, governance, resource recovery and reuse issues in providing sanitation service delivery has not resulted in a comprehensive integrated conceptual framework that captures these dynamic complexities. The ReGenSan conceptual framework aims at filling this gap. The framework seeks to capture the essential characteristics of sanitation systems, elements and structures annunciated by several authors in literature, which constitute the new sanitation paradigm presented in this paper.

The conceptual foundation of ReGenSan was derived from the General System Theory (GST), Regenerative Science and Medicine (ReSciMed) as well as Regenerative Development and Designs (ReDD). The General System Theory (GST) aligns itself with the ecological worldview, which goes beyond the reductionist-mechanistic worldview (Von Baertalaffy 1956) and embraces human development efforts with nature's potential to create new future as well as repair damages done to the biosphere. This relates to a sanitation strategy that provides new solutions as well as restorative and retrofitting of previously damaged sanitation systems (McHarg 1969, Guterstam and Todd 1990, Mitsch 1993, Mitsch and Jorgensen 1989, Kibert et al. 2002, Graham 2003, Van der Ryn and Cowan 2007, Mitsch and Jorgensen 2003, Mang and Reed 2012a, Cole 2012, Marshall and Farahbakhsh 2013).

Regenerative science and medicine (ReSciMed) also reinforces the restorative capacity of the ecological system that supports the idea of a constant state of renewal, restoration, replacement or repair (Morgan 1901, Illingworth 1974, Lenhof and Lenhoff 1991, Whithman et al. 1997, Sunderland 2008/2010, Porcellini 2009, Kragl et al. 2009, Maienschein 2011, Aida and Carrel 2014, Sampogna et al. 2015), thus, beyond designing and building new systems, restoring and retrofitting old, dysfunctional, failing and unimproved sanitation systems are also essential (Popper 1963, 2004, Edwards 2005, Reed 2007, du Plessis and Brandon 2015).

Regenerative development and design (ReDD) investigates how humans can cooperate with ecosystems to create optimum health for both human communities (physically, psychologically, socially, culturally and economically), other living organisms and systems (Zari and Jenkin 2010). It integrates the needs of society with the integrity of nature through processes that restore, renew and revitalize their own sources of energy and materials (Lyle 1994, Thayer 1994, Mang and Reed 2012). ReGenSan draws its 'psychosocio-ecophilia' principle from ReDD by emphasizing the importance of the unique and diverse human and non-human elements of each 'place' (psychosocio-ecological systems) (Cole et al. 2006). The idea of 'place' is a way for people to envision the unity of humans and natural systems (Zari and Jenkin 2010, Mang et al. 2016). In each 'place' on earth, natural and cultural systems express themselves uniquely and differently. The implication of this is that sanitation systems should be tailored to the unique characters of the 'place' by exploring the opportunities and solutions that are indigenous to the specific 'place' which is referred to in ReGenSan as 'sani-shed'. San—shed are conceived to reduce waste, maximize resources, through nutrient recycling, respect diversity, conserve energy and ensure maintenance from within (Thayer 1994, McDonough and Braungart 2001a/b). ReGenSan also draws from ConSan, EcoSan, and SuSan paradigms (see section 1.1) as it recognizes the reoccurring challenges of sanitation management over the different phases and so attempts to pull through by connecting and integrating the practical and effective aspects from each phase into a systemic whole.

4.2 The ReGenSan Conceptual Framework

ReGenSan framework is a holistic integrated sanitation system based on ecological worldview and place-scale focus where comprehensive sanitation solutions are provided within sani-sheds to mimic nature and be socially-acceptable and affordable, livelihood-supportive, technically-appropriate and enabled by 'fit-for-purpose' governance mechanisms. It consists of three sub-systems designed to support the development of novel sanitation systems, restore and upgrade old, dysfunctional and unimproved systems, ensure continuous improvement of existing improved sanitation as well as recover and reuse valuable resources from excreta and wastewater management to ensure access expansion and improved services. ReGenSan identifies and integrates three major sub-systems of sanitation: psychosocio-ecological, resource recovery, and technology. The aim is to ensure that sanitation systems do not transfer ecological and public health burdens, do not mix human waste with other wastes,

align sanitation facilities with ecological processes to ensure 'zero' or 'near minimal' discharge, and ensure that sanitation systems provide net-benefits to the people and environment (Figure 8).

Figure 8 highlights the interactions, interrelationships and interdependencies of the six dimensions of ReGenSan for research, planning, design, development and management of sanitation systems that are in harmony with the physical environment, human systems and the surrounding natural systems. The framework depicts a holistic system thinking design for the integration of technological, ecological, economic, psychosocial and political systems for planning, designing and management of sanitation systems at scale. The unbroken links and circular shape of the framework indicate the inter-synergistic linkages between the five dimensions needed for the sustainability of sanitation systems as well as improvement of service and expansion of access.

Figure 8: Conceptual framework of ReGenSan designed for the acceleration of sanitation coverage and service improvement

The double straight arrows indicate the interactive feed-back mechanisms inherent among the five dimensions of the framework. The centre has the psychosocio-ecophilia (psychological-socio-cultural-economic-ecological) and is the starting point of ReGenSan that feeds the other five dimensions and connects to all of them with a feed-back loop. This is because the first step to achieving the goal of ReGenSan is a deeper understanding of the psychosocio-ecophilia of the 'place'. Connecting between the other dimensions are the single broken arrows indicating that there should be equal and/or balanced considerations of the six dimensions in the planning, design and development of future sanitation technologies as well as retrofitting of dysfunctional and unimproved sanitation systems to achieve the aspirations of SDG 6, that is, improved and expanded access to sanitation services

universally. The framework embraces diagnostic (Ostrom 2007), prescriptive (Cookey et al. 2016b) and normative (Pahl-Wostl 2009) analytical approaches designed to deliver comprehensive integrated and adaptive sanitation solutions.

4.3 Elements of the framework

These include sub-systems, dimensions and components that constitute as follows:

4.3.1 Socio-ecological sub-system consists of two dimensions: psychosocio-ecophilia (system of the place) and governance. The sub-system seeks to provide an understanding of the multi-faceted and multilevel interactive effects of psychosocial, cultural, economic, and ecological issues that influence the whole spectrum of sanitation science, governance, practice and technology (Whittington et al. 1993, Ostrom 2009, Ostrom and Cox 2010, van Vliet et al. 2011, Hinkel et al. 2014, Partelow 2016).

4.3.1.1 Psycho-socio-ecophilia (PSEP) dimension - It provides contextual and behavioural perspectives as well as introduces psycho-socio-ecological-technical variables in the assessment and decision-making for sanitation solutions. It emphasizes the importance of 'place-scale' with focus on providing sanitation solutions within the 'sani-sheds', which ensures that sanitation systems connect with the psychosocio-ecological characteristics of the locality (Whittington et al. 1993, Kellert et al. 2008, Mang and Reed 2012b) to sustain the essential functions and processes of the ecosystem (Lyle 1984, 1994, Van der Ryn and Cowan 1996). Ambitious sustainability goals can only be fulfilled by co-design of sanitation technology with potential users in the 'system of the place' (Tobias et al. 2017). ReGenSan argues that sanitation systems should be designed to suit 'place' because the diversity of social and ethnic groups existing in any locality, greatly influence appropriate design, access, acceptability, affordability, construction and use of such systems (Whittington et al. 1993, Raven 2007, Hegger et al. 2007, Larsen et al. 2010, Domènech and Saurí 2010, McConville et al. 2014).

The 'place-scale' based solutions in 'sani-sheds' are logical units or catchment areas for providing sanitation solutions in ReGenSan. Mara and Alabaster (2008) proposed a paradigm shift from individual household sanitation solutions to groups of households to ensure significant cost-savings and overcome the challenges of sanitation solutions at household levels (Zurbrugg and Tilley 2009). The sani-shed concept provides the opportunity for benefit-sharing from the valued-added of sanitation services and products (Savenije and Zaag 2008) and could also form linkages between sanitation solutions and end-users while also addressing all issues of psychosocio-cultural concerns and standards whether at 'community scale' or 'neighborhood scale' (Shove 2003). They could then become a potential strong driving force for the needed transition (Spaaragaren et al. 2007) for planning, operations, maintenance and cost recovery where stakeholders are empowered to make choices about what kind of sanitation systems they wish to use and how it will be managed (Ferguson et al. 2003).

4.3.1.2 Governance dimension - Governance enhances the effectiveness and efficiency of sanitation operational responsibilities (i.e. the day-to-day functionality of the service delivery) and fit-for-purpose institutional arrangements (i.e. the formal and informal institutional context that helps or hinders the successful delivery of the day-to-day activities) (Kooiman 2003, Schertenleib 2005, Maurer et al. 2012, Starkl et al. 2013, Ross et al. 2014, Joshi et al. 2015). It also encompasses arrangements for ownership, management and operations, institutional contexts and regulatory frameworks (including meeting requirements on service standards, resource recovery, emission standards, pricing guidelines and cost recovery (Kooiman 2003, Schertenleib 2005, Luthi et al. 2011, Maurer et al. 2012, Starkl et al. 2013, Ross et al. 2014, Galli et al. 2014, Tilley et al. 2014, Rodic 2015). It could also support and indicate technology selection and update as well as financial mechanisms for sanitation solutions.

4.3.2 Resource recovery sub-system - focuses on how to recover valuable resources in human excreta and urine in order to ensure that sanitation systems minimize depletion of the natural resources and environmental degradation. Recovering and reusing the valuable resources present in excreta, urine and wastewater contributes to resource efficiency and improves food security (Anderson et al. 2016a/b).

4.3.2.1 Resource recovery and reuse (RRR) dimension - facilitates a shift from the design-for-disposal to design-

for-reuse. This approach effectively shifts the goal of sanitation from been solely on safe disposal of waste to maximizing the extent to which embodied resources are safely captured and allocated to deliver public and environmental health benefits. It has the potential to contribute productively to local economies and livelihoods (Murray and Buckley 2009) and is characterized by the process of 'sanitise and recycle', based on preventing pollution through nutrients recovery for food production in local communities (Haq and Cambridge 2012) and producing water, nutrients, organic matter, energy and other valuable minerals from human waste and wastewater (Bahri 1999, Lazarova et al. 2001, Lens et al. 2001, Kujawa-Roeleveld and Zeeman 2006, Jenkins and Sugden 2006, Maurer et al. 2012, Zeeman 2012, Wielemaker et al. 2016, Simha et al. 2016). RRR approaches are not techno-centric or toilet-focus, but centre on resources and their management (Andersson et al. 2016) and have the capacity to act across the whole spectrum of the sanitation cycle (Esrey 2002, Lens et al. 2001, SuSanA 2008, Larsen et al. 2013, Brands 2014).

4.3.3 Technology sub-system - is the configurations of technologies, infrastructures and services combined to treat human excreta/urine from the point of generation to the final point of reuse or disposal. It includes an extensive range of possible combinations of technical components comprising means of storage, conveyance and treatment in both sewer and non-sewer systems to deliver the most appropriate and best applicable technologies (Zurbrugg and Tilley 2009, Maurer et al. 2012, Tilley et al. 2014a/b, Ramoa et al. 2015). ReGenSan technology encompasses the entire sanitation value chain of 'users' interface-drop/or flush-store-treat-recover-utilize'. Economic, social, cultural and institutional contexts are characterized by multidimensional technological characteristics (place, scale and process), management and governance, financial arrangements and organizational set-up as well as active involvement of the end-users (Grubler 1998, Oosterveer and Spaargaren 2010, Altaf 2011, Starkl et al. 2015). There are three dimensions to this sub-system: Nouveau Design and Technology (NDT), Restorative Design and Technology (RDT), and Existing Improved Design and Technology (EIDT).

4.3.3.1 Existing Improved Design and Technology (EIDT) dimension - focuses on continuous improvement of the currently adjudged improved sanitation (safely managed, basic and limited services) facilities estimated to be used by 5 billion people (JMP 2015, WHO/UNICEF 2017) as well as ensuring an effective and efficient faecal sludge management for the estimated 2.7 billion people using on-site sanitation worldwide (Strande, 2014, Nakagiri et al. 2016). The cardinal rule of EIDT is to ensure long-term sustainability of sanitation services and avoid the risk of 'slippage' - a term coined in India to refer to the slipping back of a community from 'fully covered with improved services' to 'partially or non-covered' (Lockwood and Smits 2011, UN-Water and WHO 2012, Verhagen and Carrasco 2013, Rosenqvist et al. 2016). This is achieved through standard operations and maintenance and enhanced forward advancement on the sanitation ladder (Ghosh and Elvira 2011) by implementing improved faecal sludge management (Exley et al. 2014, Strande, 2014, Nakagiri et al. 2016) as well as ensuring that strategies are developed for retrofitting resource recovery and reuse solutions into improved sanitation facilities to address the challenge of faecal sludge management. It aims to address the problem of sewer infrastructures that do not deliver standard effluent treatment (Starkl et al. 2013) but rather discharge untreated wastewater (World bank 2003, Nhapi et al. 2006, Hutton et al. 2007, Joint Monitoring Programme 2012, Baum et al. 2013, Nasubuga et al. 2016) as well as issues of actual use, cleanliness, quality of latrines/toilets, handwashing, hygiene promotion, behavioural change, facilities' integrity, quality control and assurance (Gine et al. 2011, Exley et al. 2015).

4.3.3.2 Restorative design and technology (RDT) dimension - is an all-encompassing strategy that includes such concepts as: repair, retrofit, revitalize, rehabilitate, and upgrade. RDT seeks to retrofit unimproved and dysfunctional sanitation systems as well as support mitigation and remediation of polluted/degraded sites damaged by existing sanitation practices (Mang and Reed 2012a/b, Jenkin and Pedersen 2009). This strategy is necessary in view of the large population (2.4 billion) with inadequate and dysfunctional sanitation infrastructures (JMP 2015). The pressing goal is to better understand the reasons for continued system failure and how they could be avoided in the future (Starkl et al. 2013). Restorative designs arise due to structural inadequacies, material degradation, poor construction and workmanship as well as aging facilities and lack of operations and maintenance (Brikke 2000, Brepolsa et al.

2008, Cookey et al. 2016a), which increase exposure to pathogens present in unconfined or poorly disposed human excreta (Cairncross and Feachem 1993, Boschi-Pinto et al. 2006, Ekane et al. 2014). RDT will ensure sustainability of sanitation systems to deliver services at an appropriate level of hygiene, quality, quantity, convenience, comfort, continuity, efficiency, and reliability; and the institutionalization of complete coverage of operations, maintenance, administration and replacement strategies (Brikke 2000).

RDT advocates for retrofitting and upgrading of existing wastewater treatment systems to meet stringent treatment requirements, increasing hydraulic and/or organic loading capacity, improving poor performance due to improper plant designs and/or operations, elongating expiry lifespan of aging treatment plants and changing effluent limitations and wastewater treatment trends (USEPA 1974, Brepolsa et al. 2008, El-Sheikh 2011, Bozkurt et al. 2015). RDT also aims to address the challenges of onsite systems, especially the unimproved systems that are poorly designed, constructed, operated and maintained (Pham and Kuyama 2013, Mjoli 2012, Joint Monitoring Programme, 2008/2012/2015, Giné-Garriga et al. 2017) as well as improved systems that do not deliver, especially where local context are ignored (Starkl et al. 2013).

4.3.3.3 *Nouveau design and technology (NDT) dimension* - addresses a spectrum of emerging technological novel solutions based on the core principles of regenerative sanitation. It seeks to develop sanitation technologies that integrate eco-efficiency with ecologically-based approaches that mimic nature to deliver improved functional systems peculiar to local contexts. The strategic role of NDT is to contribute to the development of innovative solutions for the 700 million people that missed the MDG, new development areas as well as the 892 million people who have no facilities at all and are exposed to open defecation (JMP 2015, WHO/UNICEF 2017). Additional core values and principles of NDT include: appropriateness, end-users' preference, no mixing of human faeces with other waste, no-linear-flow, no-harm-to-environment and public health, no-transfer-of-burden, resource recovery and reuse, energy and water conservation, etc. It explores ways to develop sanitation technologies and systems that view toilets within a service chain extending to the final point of disposal or end-use of excreta-driven products (Tilley et al 2014) on 'place and scale based' and not 'one-cap-fits-all' (Lyle 1994, Mang and Reed 2012a, Dias 2015). It also advocates for affordable technologies and systems that are resources reclaimable (Gretchen 2012, Sunita 2012, van Loosdrecht Brdjanovic 2014, Fan et al. 2017), support food production and prevent environmental pollution while minimizing the demand on other resources (Zhou et al. 2010, Fan et al. 2017).

Depending on the possibilities of the opportunity in the 'place', NDT is to provide solutions at a scale in sani-sheds, taken into account the PSEP as well as incorporate RRR at source (Spaargaren et al. 2006). Thus, within a sani-shed, there might be several different technologies in operation with each responding to local conditions, but playing its part in the larger whole (Lyle 1994). NDT system sets extensive range of possible combinations of psycho-socio-ecological-technical components adapted from the concepts and principles of regenerative development and designs. The process may include: storage (stabilization process), assimilation (mineralization), conversion (biomass production), filtration (polishing) and distribution of the recovered resources as well as emission into the environment. A combination that treats human excreta/urine from the point of generation to the final point of reuse and possible emission into the environment is considered (Lyle 1994).

NDT components and processes are: frontend, which includes users' interface; middleend which makes up storage and treatment processes; and backend, which includes resource recovery and utilization. Technology and design are structured to let nature do the work, by drawing on natural processes of decomposition to reintegrate materials into the landscape (Lyle 1994). These high level diverse and flexible decentralized processes require new forms of knowledge, expertise and decision support systems that better integrate the analysis of the technological, psychological, cultural, socio-economic and ecological issues (Hodson and Marvin 2010). These hybrid sanitation systems and technologies will be designed to replace the first decentralized generation (appropriate technologies) with a range of systems that offer more innovative solutions and alternatives both from technical and social point of views (Oosterveer and Spaargaren 2010). NDT aims to improve energy efficiency by reducing the use of high energy consumption components, encourage energy conservation through the use of renewable energy sources (solar) and the utilization of the energy generating capacity of the system. NDT will minimize transport of waste

materials from one location to another (no-transfer-of-burden) and recommend resource separation, recovery and reuse at close proximity within the locality (place-scale based) (Larsen et al. 2009, Dixon et al. 2014, Wielemaker et al. 2016).

4.4 Framework implementation process

This section provides practical process guidelines for the implementation of ReGenSan design and development. The purpose is to develop and implement ReGenSan nouveau and restorative designs and technologies that will aid expanding sanitation access and improving services as well as maintain existing improved systems through research and implementation. The steps in this process may not be conclusive, but include: Contextual analysis of the psychosocio-ecophilia (PSEP); assessment of sanitation governance; assessment of resource recovery and reuse; assessment of existing sanitation systems and technologies; identification of priority solutions (continuous improvement activities, restorative or nouveau designs and technologies; implementation of action plans; monitoring and evaluation; and operations and maintenance). The outcome should be a detailed status assessment report for intervention towards either restorative, existing or nouveau designs and technologies (GHK Research and Training 2000, ASHWAS 2011, Lüthi et al. 2011a/b, Parkinson et al. 2014, IWA 2014, ISF-UTS and SNV 2016, Bright-Davies et al. 2016) (Figure 10).

Contextual analysis of PSEP - this process starts at the 'place' where scalable solutions are produced within sanisheds. It could be 'community-scale', 'neighborhood-scale' or 'building-scale', that provides linkages between sanitation solutions and end-users (Shove 2003, Lüthi et al. 2011b) as well as ensures active and broad engagement and involvement of relevant stakeholders in decision-making process (Webbler et al. 2003, Rowe and Frewer 2000, Luyet et al. 2012, Coockey et al. 2016c, Mang et al. 2016). PSEP factors include a wide range of cultural and religious belief systems, societal values, health and hygiene practices and behaviors as well as user preferences and are linked to population and demographics (number of people per household, population density, type of housing, gender-related issues). It also includes a wide-range of influencing factors for investment in sanitation such as personal preferences, affordability, types and quality of systems, willingness to pay, livelihood activities and types of materials to be recovered from sanitation systems. Other parameters include: water-hygiene-related issues, local climate, temperature and precipitation, biological, geophysical and hydrological.

- I. Assessment of sanitation governance* – to determine the suitability and adequacy of the enabling environment for effective and efficient sanitation service delivery. A wide range of governance issues influence delivery of sanitation services including the level of government support and political will, institutional frameworks (i.e., policy, laws, regulations, guidelines and standards), enforcement and compliance mechanisms, organizational competencies, clear demarcation of roles, responsibilities of actors (formal and informal), effective and efficient planning and management systems (especially addressing the issues of human resources, knowledge, skills and capacity) as well as financing and full cost recovery (Fonseca et al. 2011, Ross et al. 2014, Joshi et al. 2015).
- ii. Assessment of resource recovery and reuse* – to explore current sanitation systems' capacity for resource recovery and reuse. In addition, the economic value of these resources and their utilization to the 'place' will be assessed in order to support fit design and technology (Murray and Buckley 2009). The assessment shall focus on determining services that sanitation by-products can provide, demand for those services, and business models for the delivering of these by-products and services, as well as designs and technologies that can deliver these services.
- iii. Assessment of existing sanitation systems and technologies* – to identify and categorize improved and unimproved as well as the failing and dysfunctional facilities. The analysis will include existing sanitation systems, practices and technologies performance as well as operations and maintenance. The effectiveness and efficiency of the current level of faecal sludge management systems shall be assessed and determined. The level of service delivery, which is basically the benefit the users derive from current sanitation systems shall also be determined. Issues like access to facilities, convenience of use and privacy, comfort, compatibility with the 'system of the place', hygiene practices as well as downstream impacts on the environment, public health and ecological systems (IWA 2014) are critical more specifically, technical norms and standards that influence

designs, operations and maintenance, whether official standards or those accepted in practice, overtime though not formally recognized (Lüthi et al. 2011a/b) will be explored. System integrity, quality control and assurance shall also be assessed while infrastructures and facilities mapping in sani-sheds could be used to identify systems types, components and other spatial information for a clearer picture. The feedback from this assessment could determine areas that need new designs and technologies, restorative and retrofitting solutions, as well as continuous improvement programs for existing improved sanitation facilities.

iv. *Identify priority solutions* - the results, findings and conclusions from the previous activities (i– vii) are put together to provide specific solutions, which are then prioritized by the stakeholders in the 'sani-shed'. The outcome of this stage may lead to continuous improvement programmes for existing facilities, restorative or nouveau design and technology solutions or all of the above. The prioritization exercise can be done either in a workshop or a series of focus group discussions or media survey. The aim is to ensure that problems considered are critical to expanding access and improving services to the users as well as solutions they are willing to support. The main outcome of this section is the production of well costed, time guided activities and programmes for implementation.

Figure 10: Integrated and multidimensional ReGenSan systems development and implementation process

- v. *Implementation of action plans* - implementing the action plan is the final stage of the planning process, which generally leads to launching of the ReGenSan project. However, after the preparation of the final draft of the ReGenSan plan, there is the need for further consultations to ensure that every stakeholder (formal and informal) is satisfied with the final product before moving forward to the development stage. Also, operations and maintenance (O/M) activities are incorporated into the programme from the inception. Implementation should include relevant sanitation promotion, advocacy and awareness programmes for all categories of stakeholders (IWA 2014).
- vi. *Monitoring and evaluation* – establishing monitoring and evaluation processes for sanitation measures and ensures that inputs and activities lead to their intended results and outcomes and adjustments are made where necessary while established goals' progress are ascertained (UNICEF 2014). It also provides opportunities (at regular intervals) to validate the logic of the ReGenSan programme, its activities and their implementation to make adjustments as needed (UNDP 2009).

The ReGenSan framework was designed to be broad enough to accommodate other existing or new frameworks for different sub-systems, dimensions and components in order to achieve the aim of the whole, i.e., access expansion and service improvement.

4.5 Applicable cases

4.5.1 Natural sewage treatment at the Lyle Center for Regenerative Studies of the California State Polytechnic University, Pomona, USA

Lyle Centre for Regenerative Studies, located on 16 acres and accommodating more than 1,600 community members within the University campus of Pomona, California in USA was set-up to develop and test regenerative technologies. The Centre operates an integrated sewage treatment aquaculture-wetlands ecosystem for food production and inorganic nitrogen removal (Costa-Pierce 1998), and is a classic illustration of an upgraded existing improved design and technology (EIDT). The governance system applied here acknowledges that the socio-ecological system is both the source and sink. By patterning the human system to match technology, felt need and the PSEP, sanitation systems are enhanced to maximize resource recovery and reuse while minimizing disposal. The use of natural systems made it possible to meet treatment requirements for a fraction of the cost of conventional methods as well as a number of other benefits. The centre achieved regenerative sewage treatment with a combination of policy and planning decisions towards using alternatives to provide effective solutions (Woltz 1998). The Centre's understanding of the biogeochemophysical characteristics of their environment as a narrow valley that receives drainage from sparse rainfall ensures that water and sewage treatment is among the major issues addressed. This captures the 'ecological' aspect of PSEP dimension that requires a better understanding of the 'system of the place'. The Lyle Centre's vast sanitation infrastructure ensures a wide range of resource recovery and reuse. The sloping valley of the Centre naturally gathers water at the bottom and so is devoted to sewage treatment and aquaculture production. In addition, the effluent is treated and used for irrigation while solar energy recovered is supplied to the community for some of their energy needs.

The sewage treatment involves three basic natural processes functioning in parallel. The aquaculture system, the surface-flow wetland system, and the rootzone system operate side-by-side with plumbing that permits their use simultaneously or alternatively, in combination or (conceivably) in sequence. This provides the flexibility needed to test the effectiveness of all the three systems according to various parameters and to compare their performance. This interesting hybrid techno-system begins with septic tanks as the first stage of treatment and produces an effluent with two-third lower solids content and one-third reduction in organics. The septic tank sludge is removed periodically (Nichols 1993) and the effluent then transferred into any of the three treatment sequences (aquaculture, surface-flow wetland, and rootzone systems). The treatment outcome achieved by this hybrid system met the requirements of the USA Clean Water Act of 1972. While this level is adequate for irrigation use, the systems are actually designed to achieve BOD₅ and suspended solids levels of ≤ 20 mg/L (Lyle 1994). The Lyle Centre is focused on working within the natural systems of the place and designed to scale as well as creating systems of technology that matches PSEP in the design of sanitation infrastructure. To a large extent then, it could be said to have covered some core principles of ReGenSan.

4.5.2 Asian Institute of Technology solar septic tank technology, Pathumthani, Thailand

Between the periods of 2012-2016, the Asian Institute of Technology (AIT) developed innovative sanitation technologies (solar septic tank, cyclone toilet and cess-to-fit technology) through a grant support from the Bill & Melinda Gates Foundation. The focus of this case is on the solar septic tank (SST) technology that could best illustrate the NDT of ReGenSan. The rationale for SST was to improve upon the performance of current traditional septic tanks that do not satisfactorily remove pathogens and organic matter due to inappropriate design and operations (Brandes 1977, Polprasert 1982, Koottatep et al 2014). This innovative technology reduces sludge accumulation by utilizing the anaerobic digestion at high temperatures of about 40-50°C to treat human waste in the septic tank. The essential benefit of this NDT over traditional septic tanks operating at ambient temperatures are: reduction of frequency of faecal sludge emptying, increased recovery of biogas production and increased inactivation of pathogens in the effluent (Pussayanavin et al. 2015). The high temperature increases the methanogenic microbial activities occurring in the sludge layers of the tank, thus, resulting in more organic degradation, less total volatile solids (TVS) and more methane production (Koottatep et al. 2015/2016). Since 2015, field testings of the SST developed at AIT have been going on at the School of Environment and Resource Development (SERD-AIT), Santavee factory and Klong Nueng community all in Thailand. These demonstrations illustrate some aspects of ReGenSan's resource recovery. Going forward, the design team is now looking at incorporating the principles of ReGenSan into the SST, making it to scale instead of just family/household. In addition, engineered wetland systems will be included for final polishing of the effluents and reuse for irrigation and aquaculture purposes based on the understanding of the PSEP dimension. This will enhance benefit-sharing, increased output of biogas production for domestic utilization, large volume of high quality effluents for food production and improved environmental quality. The SST should eventually discourage one-family-one-septic-tank syndrome highly responsible for sewage contamination in most developing countries of the world.

4.5.3 South Africa's National Sanitation Upgrading and Replacement programmes

The South African government has prioritized access to basic sanitation services in order to proffer solutions to the country's sanitation backlog (RSA 1994). This policy thrust has resulted in a number of laudable sanitation restorative programmes such as: the National Sanitation Bucket Replacement programme, resource recovery and reuse from large number of upgraded Ventilated Improved Pit (VIP) toilets and sewerage informal settlements – Cape Town's vacuum sewer. The lessons learnt from these projects expose the need for a better understanding of the PSEP and governance issues of ReGenSan and the role they play in the successful implementation of sanitation upgrading and replacement programmes.

The South Africa National Sanitation Bucket Replacement was a near classic case of RDT aimed at replacing and upgrading an estimated 252, 254 bucket toilets located across seven provinces. The bucket sanitation systems were unhygienic and expensive to maintain and violated the dignity of users and those responsible for collection and disposal (Mjoli 2012). The national programme started in 2005 and by the end of 2008 more than 91% of the target number of bucket sanitation were replaced by water-borne sanitation systems and upgraded Ventilated Improved Pit (VIP) toilets (DWA 2008a). The programme, however, faced challenges that could be attributed to a disregard of the PSEP dimension because some municipalities' bulk sewers and wastewater treatment capacities were inadequate and in some areas the available water supply could not support the new waterborne sanitation systems (Mjoli 2012). Also, in areas where upgraded VIP toilets were implemented, emptying trucks could hardly access the more than 60,000 VIPs due to the nature of houses, especially in the informal settlements and many resource recovery and reuse strategies also impacted negatively (Murray and Buckley 2009).

A recovery and reuse strategy in Mnini district of the eThekweni Municipality, which involved treating wastewater via a pond system that was then used for irrigation of a 2 ha banana and mango farm, was stalled at 75 percent completion in spite of its technical viability. The system was never commissioned because it did not comply with ReGenSan's PSEP and governance even though it fitted with the RDT component of replacement. In fact, lack of prior permissions from local traditional leaders for land use, no prior permission from local households to install irrigation systems and utilize land for agriculture as well as no approval from relevant government agencies shot

down the scheme before it could begin (Murray and Buckley 2009).

Also, installing conventional gravity sewerage in Cape Town's informal settlements proved difficult due to various social, built and natural environment challenges (Taing et al. 2013, Sonnenberg 2013). In order to resolve this problem, the Officials of the City of Cape Town (CoCT) decided to explore vacuum sewer technology as an alternative solution. However, the vacuum sewer failed immediately after its commissioning in early 2009 and so residents demanded for its removal along with its flush-toilets return the phased-out bucket-toilets (Taing 2017). The Vacuum Sewer System (VSS) was hampered from inception by users' and service-providers' (CoCT's) poor management (PSEP and governance dimensions). Residents were disposing cutlery and bricks into the system which caused flooding and blocking of sumps, malfunctioning of sensors controllers due to fats and dirt clogging the system, and overloading of vacuum pumps due to air leakages in the line (Taing et al. 2013). Other major challenges were servicing conflicts between two municipal departments over who was responsible (and therefore accountable) for planning, implementation and management of sanitation infrastructures (CoCT 2005) and operations and maintenance conflicts between the city and community over who had responsibility for cleaning and maintaining the newly installed communal toilets (DWAF 2008b). Residents have subsequently and permanently locked majority of the toilet blocks in order to prevent anyone from using them.

The South Africa challenge results when service-providers narrow-down the definition of sanitation to toilet provision and rather than service and management as well as counting on quantity of buckets and sewer replacement rather than quality, affordability and availability of technical capacity for operations and maintenance. In fact, a proper and extensive understanding of the socio-ecological system of the operating environment and the psychological, social, cultural and economic dynamics of the users could have greatly reduced the hindrances and up-scaled its chances for success. These are the issues that ReGenSan aims to address.

5.0 DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The Regenerative Sanitation concept and framework presented in this paper is innovative on four levels: (i) it offers a comprehensive, holistic, integrated and systemic outlook for sanitation management rather than a singular focus, (ii) it embraces the dynamic complexities and contextual peculiarities of 'place and scale' in delivering sanitation solutions, (iii) introduces the concept of sani-sheds, and (iv) it is also the first time the regenerative concept is applied in the field of sanitation research. ReGenSan does not seek to replace previous frameworks or paradigms, but integrates all aspects of sanitation and holistically interacts with related issues (e.g. water, health, hygiene, gender, etc.) to create a comprehensive picture of the best approach and solution for particular contexts. The need for a comprehensive, integrated and systemic framework became apparent and of utmost necessity after the dismal results of the MDGs' sanitation targets. With the recent JMP outlook, it is quite obvious that if the SDG 6 will perform better by 2030, it cannot be business as usual. Sanitation management needs its own focused solutions-provision and should also be thoroughly investigated for efficacy, effectiveness and acceptance; only then can we begin to see the much-needed and desired access expansion and service improvement.

The ReGenSan framework is unique in that it is applicable to both developed and developing countries, and to all stages, processes and cycles of delivering sanitation solutions. The framework has the potential to critically evaluate, analyze and provide credible, adequate and appropriate sanitation solutions by adopting diagnostic, prescriptive and normative analytical approaches (Ostrom 2007, Pahl-Wostl 2009, Cookey et al. 2016b). The diagnostic provides detailed existing status reports for interventions that are geared towards either restorative, existing or nouveau solutions. The prescriptive perspectives are built upon the diagnostic and play strategic roles in determining the appropriateness and adequacy of the applied interventions and at the same time promote the elements of continuous improvement, especially with the existing improved-safely managed (EIDT), retrofitting of unimproved-dysfunctional (RDT) and nouveau (NDT) sanitation systems and services as well as strategically retrofit resource recovery and reuse (RRR) into current conventional infrastructures (sewers and non-sewers). On the other hand, the normative is associated with the governance and PSEP perspectives that provide the optimum enabling and operating environment for the uptake of scalable solutions. These perspectives provide better understanding of the interconnections of knowledge among the sanitation sub-systems, dimensions and components; with overarching objectives to: (i) generate interdisciplinary system understanding for service

improvement and access expansion; (ii) develop and implement sani-shed specific methods, models and technological solutions as well as evolve contextual-dependent governance structures and strategies for place and based-scale sanitation service delivery; and (iii) integrate science-policy-technology-practice research into sanitation space through a cyclical learning process.

This ReGenSan framework has shown for the first time how socio-ecological, resource recovery and technological sanitation sub-systems are inter-synergistically linked in a systemic whole to deliver comprehensive integrated sanitation solutions. The intention is to improve management, planning and technological innovations to help guide the activities of practitioners, policy-makers and academics working in the sanitation space. For instance, the challenge of expanding access to sanitation in developing countries and addressing the impacts of conventional centralized systems in developed countries could be strategically addressed through the window of retrofitting and rehabilitation rather than building new ones. The ReGenSan framework advocates for comprehensive integration of all the components of the sanitation system to ensure the capacity of sustained service delivery as well as improve participatory processes that enhance ownership and buy-in of would-be users. The diversity that often exists in social and ethnic groups of any locality greatly influences the design, access, acceptability, affordability, construction and use of sanitation systems. Therefore, this framework will strengthen understanding of the unique dynamics-potential of a location to influence types and processes of technologies and determine systems' capacity to improve own performance, which could avoid situations like the South Africa and Thailand case scenarios, and guide designing and fitting to place systems like the Lyle Centre.

It is believed that this proposed ReGenSan framework has the potential to induce improvement and mind-change in sanitation system-thinking, management, planning and technology innovations without compromising the sustainability of the ecosystem. Also, the ReGenSan framework is broad enough to accommodate other pre-existing frameworks and perspectives as it provides functional and progressive approaches towards improving and expanding access to sanitation services at a 'scale'. The framework also provides comprehensive, explorative, experimental and descriptive assessments using qualitative and quantitative datasets for better understanding of sanitation sub-systems, dimensions and components. ReGenSan could also serve as a guide for funding/donor and intervention agencies by helping them to identify where and when funds and support for more effective and practical outcomes. It could also help to strengthen global planning and implementation towards expanding access and improving service delivery of sanitation solutions. At the same time, it could really serve as a pathway or portal for innovative designs and development of sanitation technologies and social solutions.

The major constraint, in the application of this framework is the disregard of conceptual frameworks in sanitation research. This trend is changing as we begin to see some recent upsurge of framework, perspective and paradigm researches in the sanitation space and we hope that the use of this conceptual framework will become common place. The perception of sanitation only through the lens of toilets as isolated structures for defecation with products and by-products only considered as waste and nuisances that contaminate, pollute and degrade the ecological system must change. Sanitation should rather be seen as a catalyst for systemic community regeneration and transformation. In this regard, future research could look at the following: (i) how PSEP pre-considerations can lead to practical, effective and acceptable technological solutions; (ii) designing sanitation solutions to match 'place' and 'scale'; (iii) upgrading 'EIDT' per scale and PSEP requirements per scale; (iv) retrofitting dysfunctional and failing infrastructure and facilities to fit place and scale; (v) replacing dysfunctional and failing infrastructure and facilities with NDT that fit with place and particular scale type; (vi) governance and institutional framework fit-for-place towards improving sanitation solutions and service delivery; (vii) incorporating ReGenSan into design and plans for new cities, areas, estates, apartments, which include reducing transfer of burden at final disposal (i.e., resource recovery/reuse and treatment within point of generation) as much as possible; and (viii) capacity development and training for key government officials and regulators.

6.0 REFERENCES

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